

IMPROVEMENT STRATEGY EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AT SYNTAX CORPORATION INDONESIA (SCI GROUP)

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Abstract

This study aimed to examine employee empowerment through organizational culture in improving employee performance at the Syntax Corporation Indonesia (Syntax Group). The methodology used in this research is descriptive qualitative, which analyzes data from various sources. The result is that the Syntax Group has a planned and structured organizational culture as stated in the Work Culture principles, namely Religious, Excellent Service, Innovative, Creative, Totality, and based on the value of work, that is Satisfied, Complete, and Fast. Besides that, the Syntax Group also has strategic achievements with dynamic learning, organization transformation, people empowerment, knowledge management, and technology application. This is what makes Syntax Group have very good employee performance. From these achievements, Syntax Group is committed to building human resources in accordance with the agreed principles, namely people of Syntax, people of publication, people of qualifications, people of morality, people of sharing, and people of competence. Therefore, the formation of human Syntax will give birth to competent employees, self-concept, character, knowledge, skills, and high work motivation. Based on the results of the formation of Syntax people through this organizational culture strategy, it is the key to achieving optimal company performance so that the company's quality continues to increase. Namely people of publication, people of qualifications, people of morality, people of sharing, people of competence. Therefore, the formation of human Syntax will give birth to competent employees, self-concept, character, knowledge, skills, and high work motivation.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Work Culture, Work Value, Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The role of human resources (HR) is one of capital and occupies the most important position in achieving company goals. Companies need to manage and maintain human resources to be utilized as well as possible. A company's success lies not only in technical and technological excellence but also in the role of HR, which is the most important part of achieving company success.

Increasing company productivity is urgently needed, so something or activities must be done to improve employee performance, one of which is employee empowerment. Employee empowerment is an attempt to encourage and enable individuals to take personal responsibility for their efforts to improve how they do their work and is connected to the achievement of organizational goals. The principle is that employees respond more creatively when given multiple responsibilities, encourage them to contribute, and help them derive satisfaction from their jobs. Therefore, the company usually aims to increase employee performance, motivation, commitment, and productivity through empowerment (Walton, 1985).

Employees being one of the important assets in the organization need to be invited to participate in thinking and handling strategic issues, even to the point of being given responsibility in order to achieve organizational goals. From here it is hoped that imagination, originality, initiative and creativity will emerge which will be very useful to

improve the quality of everyone and advance the progress of the organization. Therefore, the involvement and participation of all layers from the highest level to the lowest level to be able to face an increasingly severe situation together.

It is the dream of every leader in an organization to have employees who can manage themselves at work. Because, usually all leaders want employees under them to be able to work on their own initiative without having to be continuously guided, so with a little guidance it is hoped that these employees can complete tasks to the fullest.

The service sector's contribution to national GDP tends to increase from year to year. After reaching 55% in 2012, the service sector contributed 60% in 2015 and it is estimated that in the following years, the service sector's contribution to national GDP will continue to increase. Not only contributing to national GDP, the service sector is the most important sector in the economy because the service sector contributes to creating jobs and of course increasing Indonesia's competitiveness.

The growth of the service industry can be said to be rapid, meanwhile business competition in the service sector is also growing. The characteristics of services are very different from physical products. According to (Lupiyoadi & Hamdani, 2013), the characteristics of services include services that are intangible, cannot be stored (storability), and change or vary (customization), and do not last long. Therefore, in order to compete and dominate the market, service companies must provide the best service for customers. Likewise, one of them is in educational consulting services, where consumers in choosing educational consulting services depend on many things, including factors of service and convenience, reliability, cost, flexibility, speed, and so on.

Companies engaged in the service industry are currently implementing employee empowerment as a step for organizations to participate more effectively and make things run well and smoothly. Empowerment teaches employees how to make decisions and take responsibility for the results they work on. Through empowerment, it is ensured that organizations can obtain and retain employees with quality, skills, knowledge and abilities, as well as employ employees effectively and efficiently. Regarding the development and growth of the service industry, how can service industry companies manage their employees through employee empowerment.

Conflict can be broadly defined as a mismatch of interests or unequal goals (Korsgaard, Soyoun Jeong, Mahony, & Pitariu, 2008). Conflict has two dimensions namely, cognitive conflict that is rooted in the essence of the task and affective conflict, which comes from differences of opinion between team members on personal or emotional issues. Cognitive conflict refers to differences of opinion between team members about viewpoints, opinions, and ideas while affective conflict refers to differences of opinion between team members about personal or emotional issues. Group conflict in the team empowerment process will reduce cohesiveness and effectiveness in carrying out duties and responsibilities in the workplace (Langfred, 2000: 11).

Through employee empowerment, employees are able to do actual empowerment in the workplace, especially in service business companies, so that employees can feel the positive impact of empowering employees both individually and in teams and also employees can overcome work conflicts which increase employee productivity and organizational performance. Occurs between individuals within the organization. Through authorization, the company provides opportunities for employees to plan and

control the implementation of work plans that are their responsibility, so as to improve employee performance, productivity and organizational performance.

Employee empowerment is often ignored by companies, even though employee empowerment is also the key to company success. Empowerment of employees according to (Mowen, Hansen, & Heitger, 2016) is the granting of authority to employees to plan (planning), control (controlling) and make decisions on the work that is their responsibility, without having to obtain explicit authorization from the manager above. So employees here are given trust by superiors so as to make these employees have a sense of responsibility which has a positive impact on employees because employees will feel valued by superiors. (Spreitzer, Kizilos, & Nason, 1997) also defines empowerment as a process in which individuals have the power to participate directly to control and influence an event that has a direct effect on their lives. Therefore, employee empowerment is carried out by exploring the potential that exists within employees, then empowerment means developing power, not just distributing existing power and which is already owned by management.

A company will run well and optimally, when supported by various potential sources such as human resources (employees). To achieve the goals of the agency, it is necessary to have competent human resources who play an important role in assisting every activity of groups, organizations and communities to achieve goals. Employee competence needs to be considered in every agency or organization, because quality and quantity are also seen from the ability and competence of employees in carrying out the responsibilities they have. To be able to mobilize employees to work more effectively, it is necessary to foster and utilize existing human resources so that they become employees who have high loyalty and adequate quality and ability in accordance with the fields and skills possessed,

Various problems can affect the achievement of company goals. One of them is the Human Resources factor. This factor has a strategic role and function in improving the quality of company services. However, what is problematic for HR is performance issues, where these problems can be influenced by various factors as well. One of the important roles that must be emphasized by a company in order to achieve its goals is to create a work environment, both a physical work environment and a non-physical work environment. Such as the perceptions of employees regarding the work environment that they get so that employees can provide different assessments of all aspects of the work environment.

The creation of a comfortable, safe and enjoyable work environment is one of the company's ways to improve the performance of its employees. According to Mangkunegara what is meant by performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Employees can maximize their performance with the support of an appropriate work environment. The influence of the work environment on employee performance can be seen from the employees of the North Malang Pratama Tax Service Office, namely being able to provide maintenance of a good work environment which has been implemented in the company in providing services in the field of taxation (Rahmawanti, 2014).

Mangkunegara further explained that performance can be interpreted as the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Employees who have good

performance are employees who have good quality work, large quantity of work, good or friendly attitude, reliable, initiative, diligent, always present at work and have the potential to progress. In the end, employees who have good performance can create competitiveness for the company, because they can carry out activities according to the targets set. These advantages can make the company win the competition and satisfy customers. On the contrary, (Callista, 2016).

Human Resources (HR) is a central factor in an organization. Whatever the form and purpose, the organization is made based on various visions for the benefit of humans and in carrying out its mission it is managed and regulated by humans as a strategic resource in institutional and organizational activities. Without humans in a company, it will not be possible for the company to develop and progress as expected. Success in achieving company goals is largely determined by the performance of its employees.

Then another thing in measuring the success of the performance of individual employees, teams or organizations lies in productivity. The level of success of a company can be measured based on the company's productivity of each individual who works in it, where individual productivity is a measure of the company's productivity as a whole. Individual productivity is a comparison of output effectiveness (maximum performance achievement) with efficiency being one input (labor) which includes quantity, quality in a certain time unit (Mulyadi Day, 2010).

The goals of a company will be achieved if employees get job satisfaction as expected. Gumilar stated that if someone becomes an employee who has joined a forum, namely an organization, of course he will form a job expectation which consists of wants, desires, needs and past experiences into the organization or company where he is currently taking shelter. These job expectations will later be related to a person's job satisfaction, in this case the organization's employees, where the expectations that arise will be compared with the rewards of work that form a suitability, namely job satisfaction. (Mahendrawan & Indrawati, 2015).

Job satisfaction is a feeling that arises from within a person, where he evaluates the characteristics of the job positively. Rivai stated that job satisfaction is an overflow of feelings of likes and dislikes, satisfaction or dissatisfaction with one's work. According to Robins job satisfaction can be measured from the nature of work, supervision, current pay, promotion opportunities and temporary co-workers. In addition Afrizal showed that compensation is another factor that affects job satisfaction (Mahendrawan & Indrawati, 2015).

The problem of job satisfaction felt by employees can reduce organizational commitment or increase organizational commitment. Judging from the advantages of job satisfaction, if someone has found a sense of satisfaction with their work, it is assumed that the individual will have a high commitment to his work. Phenomena related to job satisfaction, where employees are explained that the workload given is too heavy not comparable to what is given by the company. In addition, there is also a lack of job satisfaction if, on the contrary, a decrease in a person's satisfaction with work will reduce individual attachment to his work (Suputra & Sriathi, 2018).

To achieve and produce a very good service quality, a service company must understand and implement all the dimensions of service quality appropriately, because customers in assessing the quality of a company's services, they use their perceptions by seeing and feeling the dimensions of service quality offered by a company. Responding to this is not just theory but can be applied in real terms in the

corporate world. In the service industry to understand the target customer's perception of their service needs and also to provide a measure of the organization's service quality. The thing that needs to be understood is how to internally understand employee perceptions of service quality with the aim of achieving service improvement.

The service quality of a company must be continuously maintained and improved because customers expect to get a good service even beyond what they expect so that customers will be satisfied with the service company. The definition of quality itself according to Kotler and Keller is "Quality is the totality of features and characteristics of a product or service that bears on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs"(Widjoyo, 2013). From this explanation it can be concluded that quality is the whole of the features and characteristics of a product or service that has the ability to satisfy needs.

According to Tjiptono stated that "service quality is the fulfillment of customer needs and desires and the accuracy of delivery to offset customer expectations". Thus, there are two main factors that influence service quality, namely expected service and perceived service. In addition, Alma said that "a service company must maintain the quality of the services offered must be above the competition and greater than what consumers imagine"(Widjoyo, 2013). Therefore, from these assumptions, how can employee performance be improved?

Syntax Group is one of the companies that is very concerned about the field of educational consulting services, starting from the products provided to customers such as improving the quality of higher education management, improving the quality of scientific journal publications and publishing books, implementing IT systems, increasing sustainability and developing higher education and implementing entrepreneurship. in economic institutions. To answer all these roles, Syntax Group has a complete division and holding for a company in providing assistance to educational institutions, entrepreneurship and empowering Human Resources (HR) within them. The Syntax Group company has 4 institutions, namely consulting institutions (Division of Quality Assurance Management and Educational Development Consultant division), Publication institutions (holding Ridwan Institute, holding Green Publisher Indonesia, Indonesian Publications, Riviera Publishing and International Journal Labs), economic institutions (Participatory Economics and Investment Agency) and IT and creative institutions (Intention and Seo Labs), each institution has a division or holding within it. This company works with clients to help solve problems and provide the right solutions. The projects undertaken by Syntax Group are quite large and broad, the company's targets are National and International. This company works with clients to help solve problems and provide the right solutions. The projects undertaken by Syntax Group are quite large and broad, the company's targets are National and International. This company works with clients to help solve problems and provide the right solutions. The projects undertaken by Syntax Group are quite large and broad, the company's targets are National and International.

The success of the syntax group is inseparable from the performance achievements both individually and in groups. Achieving good performance is accompanied by an increase in employee competence that is evenly distributed. Based on research conducted by researchers on the syntax group, the human resources they have are 120 people with an education classification.

Table 1: Classification of HR Education in Syntax Group Companies

Educational Classification			
Senior High School	Bachelor Degree	Master Degree	Doctoral Degree
49	65	7	1

Source: Processed data

The HR target for the company in 2021 is that there are 30 employees who are continuing their Masters studies and 30 people who are continuing their Bachelors studies have not been achieved, due to various factors, namely 1) the HR mindset is not yet open, 2) lack of confidence in academic abilities, 3) Profiling is not optimal Human resources related to employee performance competencies that make there is no increase in competence. HR competency improvement strategies are still abstract in nature, there is no profiling, HR competency roadmaps, talent management and strategies for how HR is able to have various competencies in their field of work, so that they affect company performance and turnover.

According to (Sedarmayanti, 2017) said that competence is closer to the ability or capability that is applied and produces employees or leaders or officials who show maximum performance is called having competence. Competence is the ability of an individual as indicated by good performance in his position or job. Like the theory of (Abdi & Wahid, 2018) states that if employees have high competence so that it can provide an increase in the results of work owned by employees. This statement is supported by the results of empirical research from (Kadir, 2018) find competence that has a positive and significant effect on the work results of its subordinates.

Based on the explanation of the background of the problems that have been explained, therefore, it is deemed necessary to carry out research related to employee empowerment in the field of organizational culture which will improve employee performance. Theoretically, this research is based on theories concerning employee performance and employee empowerment in various fields such as organizational culture, work environment productivity, performance satisfaction, service quality, educational qualifications, competence and work competence. It has offense in the problem of improving employee performance.

Performance is the result of an employee's work in a company that is in accordance with their role in carrying out the work, the experience they have at work and the timeliness in completing the work. The tasks given are expected to provide performance in accordance with the demands that have been carried out, which results will determine employees in achieving performance. In addition, performance is also the result of work that has been achieved by someone for organizational goals within the company in the form of work results that are directly obtained and able to adapt to someone who will bring cooperation in completing company work. This can be short term or long term which can improve work results both individually and in groups.

Based on the background above, the author wishes to research the Employee Performance Improvement Strategy at the Syntax Group Corporation Cirebon Company.

2. LITERATURE STUDY

2.1 Human Resource Management

Human resource management (HRM) is the process of acquiring, training, evaluating, compensating employees and maintaining their employment relationship, employee health and safety, and matters relating to fairness. (Dessler, 2015 14th edition). Covers important aspects of the organization, including how to carry out job analysis, plan workforce requirements and recruit job candidates, select job candidates, find and train new employees, manage compensation and salaries (employee compensation), provide incentives and benefits, evaluate performance, and how to communicate, Train and develop employees, and how to build employee commitment.

The important role of HR in the old paradigm is to focus on production, finance and marketing functions, not the type of effective management because it is short term oriented. In the new paradigm, the role of HR is concentrated in the function of human resources, this is an effective type of management because it is long term oriented (Pfeffer, Soetjipto, & Handoko, 2003). Human resources have changed its meaning to personnel administration, namely personnel management. Through human resource management, 'people management' is now used in several organizations. Over time, the function of human resources initially only as an administrative function (keeping personal records, processing wages), then has a conversion function, namely the use of human resources within the organization for specific purposes, such as maximizing profits, shareholders. human resource function is part of the organization's strategy to achieve organizational goals, related to the organization's strategic objectives, and provides important input to achieve competitive advantage. (Ásványi, 2022).

2.2 Employee Empowerment

The concept and definition of employee empowerment is the process of transferring power and responsibility to lower-level employees in the organizational hierarchy. This is the transfer of power from the manager to the subordinates. This is when a person has been working for several years, and he has developed ideas, knowledge, skills, thorough transferability and puts everything in his hands. If employees are given full responsibility for the work they do, employees who have the power and responsibility can make their own decisions and complete their work effectively and efficiently. Employee expectations are power, authority, recognition, status, and responsibility. When they get this, they will try their hardest to realize their potential.

According to (Greasley et al., 2008) empowerment programs aim to delegate power and authority to subordinates and share responsibility with them. All of these can increase the status and recognition of authorized employees. The mentality that employees are ready to complete tasks and do their best to achieve personal goals, team goals and organizational goals. (Randolph & Sashkin, 2002) asserts that employee empowerment is the transfer of power from superiors to employees. Empowerment is the process of providing greater autonomy by sharing relevant information and controlling factors that affect job performance. (Ghosh, 2013) defines empowerment as a process of increasing the self-efficacy of organizational members by identifying conditions that encourage impotence. In terms of empowerment, (Burke, 2005) argues that empowerment means giving power and empowerment. More emphasis is placed on the transfer of power and authority to employees through management. Empowerment is a combination of the mental state of subordinates and is influenced by the behavior of superiors.

2.3 Employee performance

Performance is the result of work achieved by someone based on job requirements. A job has certain requirements to be carried out in achieving goals which are also known as work standards. Performance standard is the expected level of a particular job to be completed, and is a comparison of the goals or targets to be achieved. Work results are the results obtained by an employee in carrying out work according to job requirements or performance standards. An employee is said to be successful in carrying out his work or having good performance, if the work results obtained are higher than the performance standard (Wake Up, 2008).

According to Mathis and Jackson (Ayunda, Siswati, & Faith, 2021) employee performance indicators are:

- 1) Quality, can be measured from the employee's perception of the quality of work produced and the perfection of the task of the skills and abilities of employees. The results of the work done are close to perfect or meet the expected goals of the work.
- 2) Quantity, measured by the employee's perception of the number of assigned activities and their results.
- 3) Punctuality, measured from the employee's perception of an activity completed from the beginning of time until it becomes output. Can finish at a predetermined time and maximize the time available for other activities.
- 4) Effectiveness, maximize the use of resources and time in the organization to increase profits and reduce losses.
- 5) Presence, the level of employee presence in the company can determine employee performance.

2.4 Performance Improvement Strategy through Organizational Culture

Mintzberg expanded the concept of strategy and defined strategy by paying attention to the various dimensions of the concept of strategy, which was quoted by Ismail Solihin, that Mintzberg called "5 P's of Strategy", (Ismail, 2012).

Jeff Cartwright defines organizational culture cited by Wibowo that culture is a strong determinant of people's beliefs, attitudes and behavior, and its influence can be measured through how people are motivated to respond to their cultural environment. On that basis, Cartwright defines culture as an organized collection of people who share the same goals, beliefs and values, and can be measured in terms of their influence on motivation. (Rizky, Wahjusaputri, & Wibowo, 2020).

3. METHODS

The research taken by researchers is non-positivist. This study uses a qualitative approach, namely trying to understand phenomena in their natural settings and contexts (not in a laboratory) where researchers do not try to manipulate the observed phenomena (Leady & Ormrod, 2005). Qualitative research seeks to explore and understand the meaning of different truths by different people. In a qualitative approach, one type of approach that is often used is the case study approach.

Case study is a research strategy in which the researcher carefully investigates a programme, event, activity, process or group of individuals. Cases are limited by time

and activity, and researchers collect complete information using various data collection procedures based on a predetermined time (Rahardjo, 2017). According to Yin (2015) case study research is a research approach that explores a phenomenon in its context by using data from various sources. In the case study approach the main focus is to emphasize the importance of cases at each stage of the research process and answer research problems that begin with the question words how or why (Creswell & Poth, 2007).

Based on the information above, it can be concluded that qualitative descriptive research is a series of activities to obtain data that is as it is without being in certain conditions where the results emphasize meaning. Here, the researcher uses a qualitative descriptive research method because this research explores the phenomenon of the employee empowerment process in the dimensions of competence both in terms of planning, implementation and evaluation carried out by the Syntax Group Company. Therefore, the authors use more interpersonal approaches in this study, which means that during the research process, the authors will make more contact with parties who are in the research location.

4. RESULT

4.1 General Description of The Research Object

This research examines the strategies for improving employee performance through organizational culture at the Sintax Group Company. Research that provides a comprehensive explanation of the relationship between organizational culture that has a direct effect on employee performance at the Syntax Group service company. The company has 5 (five) divisions namely Quality Assurance Management, Educational Development Consultant, HR Career, Lecturer Career Consultant and Creative Media and 7 (seven) holdings namely Ridwan Institute, Indonesian Publication, Indonesian Green Publisher, Seo Labs, International Journal Labs, Riviera Publishing and Intention. This detailed description is described in the Syntax Group company profile.

4.2 History of Syntax Corporation Indonesia

Syntax Corporation Indonesia, hereinafter referred to as the syntax group, is a company that was originally established in 2015 founded by Dr. Taufik Ridwan, M.Hum and legalized through the Notary Deed of Mrs. Sri Ishana, SH., MH with the type of company in limited partnership (CV). The location of the company is located in Greenland Sendang Residence, Sendang Village, Sumber District, Cirebon Regency, where the scope of its business is engaged in the fields of educational consulting, publication, IT and training. Over time Syntax Group developed and its legality was renewed in 2018 by Notary Solichin, SH., M.Kn and its business scope began to develop along with the increasing development of international journal publications, IT Solutions, establishing Educational Institutions starting from Kindergarten, Elementary, Middle School and Vocational Schools ,

In short, the establishment of Syntax at first was not to become an Education consultant or publishing and publication, but instead focused on the IT and training fields. It has been running since 2013 and officially has legality in 2015 under the name CV. Syntax Computama, then made changes in 2018 to CV. Syntax Corporation Indonesia. Syntax has a logo as a spirit and branding syntax in providing an introduction to many parties. The meaning of the Syntax logo is found in the 2021 Company Profile.

Figure 3: Syntax Group Logo

The meaning of the logo belonging to the Syntax group is as follows:

- 1) The Syntax logo consists of a combination of 20 squares forming the letters S da C as the initials of the company, Syntax Corporation. With a green color to give the spirit of youth, growth and creativity.
- 2) In the logo there are 5 boxes of different colors connected by lines to form a network. We agree that today is the era of synergy, so we grow with partners, not on our own.
- 3) Syntax in its original sense is the rules for writing sentences in a particular language, which are more often used in terms of computer programming languages. That the name Syntax means technology, as our characteristic is present with technology.
- 4) We have a tagline that is easy for everyone chosen with the hope that the presence of Syntax Corporation Indonesia can help anyone who is still within our range of competence, so that it is more useful for everyone.

Syntax Group has full confidence in providing services by having 5 (five) work cultures that have become the basis and are applied in every work activity including 1) religious 2) excellent service 3) creative 4) innovative and 5) totality, this work culture is the spearhead from the running of the company that continues to grow and advance. Syntax has also carried out service performance with the Fast Complete Satisfaction (CTP) model, this model is one of the company's uniqueness in providing customer satisfaction (user satisfaction). Indicators of the achievement of the CTP model start from carrying out the collaboration process, providing work progress reports consistently and periodically weekly and monthly to various parties as well as providing award certificates and products that have been completed.

4.3 Syntax Group Vision and Milestones

4.3.1 Vision of Syntax Group:

Become a leading company in Indonesia based on Learning Organization in 2025.

4.3.2 Mission of Syntax Group:

- 1) Creating learning dynamics (learning dynamics) that continue to make improvements and improvements
- 2) Creating a culture of organizational transformation (transformation organization) consistently
- 3) Advocating for human resource empowerment (people empowerment) as a contribution to the progress of the nation
- 4) Creating effective and efficient corporate knowledge management
- 5) Accelerate technology application according to the principle of change

The general description of the vision carried by Syntax Corporation Indonesia is based on an era full of disruptions for all companies to make a change, Syntax Corporation Indonesia is here to answer the challenges of that era, by creating a learning organization-based company. Learning Organization is meant that the company continues to carry out a learning culture so that it continues to grow and develop. For us learning is the main key for all stages of the best performance.

The vision is implemented on the mission owned by the Syntax Corporation company totaling 5 (five)

- 1) Creating learning dynamics that continue to make improvements and improvements.
- 2) Creating a culture of organizational transformation (transformation organization) consistently.
- 3) Advocating for human resource empowerment (people empowerment) as a contribution to the progress of the nation.
- 4) Creating an effective and efficient management of corporate knowledge resources
- 5) Accelerate technology application according to the principle of change

4.4 Work Culture from Syntax Group:

- 1) Religious; Religious culture is a way of thinking and acting of corporate citizens based on religious values (religiousness). This religious culture is an effort to realize the values of religious teachings as a tradition in behavior and organizational culture which is followed by all residents in the Syntax Group company. Thus this religious culture as a pattern of behavior in accordance with the values of Islamic religious teachings which is carried out together in the long term and carried out continuously so as to form a habit and become a tradition that is followed by all components of the Syntax Group company.
- 2) Excellent service; is the maximum form of service provided by Syntax Group. This is done to increase customer trust. Excellent service is also defined as Syntax Group's excellent service to the company's service users. The form of excellent service consists of many kinds, according to the type of service provided by Syntax Group. This excellent service is provided in the form of maximum service for Syntax Group customer satisfaction.
- 3) Innovative; that is cultivated by Syntax Group is a work culture that creates and discovers new things. For every employee of the Syntax Group company, they are directed to innovate in their work. Therefore every Syntax Group employee needs more creativity and more willingness to take risks than the implementation of a typical project.
- 4) Creative; this culture is the work culture of Syntax Group employees. Employees always give ideas for concepts and plans for the advancement of the Syntax company. This idea is needed in one's thinking and also in the work of a person in solving social problems that are developing.
- 5) Totality; Crocodile is the totality of work at the Syntax Company one of the cultures is working hard, giving extra effort, being actively involved, focusing on work, being physically present and giving energy to what is being done. Employee with high work totality identify their own work and are motivated in carrying out their work.

They tend to work harder and more productively than other employees and are more likely to result in customer satisfaction and organizational goals being achieved

4.5 Work Values from Syntax Group:

- 1) Fast; Syntax company provides fast and precise service. Prioritizing customer satisfaction, completing earlier than the desired target
- 2) complete; Syntax company provides complete service. Without leaving homework and giving maximum results
- 3) Satisfied; Syntax company prioritizes job satisfaction, or service user satisfaction

Based on the 5 mission indicators that have been used as the basis for implementing and reflecting all activities in the Syntax environment. One of the achievements of learning organizations is learning dynamic, which means that the whole team must carry out continuous learning dynamics in order to create human learners. Organization transformation is expected that the organization will continue to transform according to the needs of the times and users. Externally, knowledge management is intended to implement existing knowledge management within the organization and technology application is intended for companies to continue to apply technology applications in the process of technological progress.

The presence of Syntax Group is expected to help many parties, in line with the tagline ease for everyone. Because the real value for us is how much it benefits others and the impact on others. The form of realization of Syntax Group's vision and mission until 2025 is described in the milestone mountain starting from 2020 (Syntax Creative), 2021 (Syntax Established), 2022 (Syntax Admiration), 2023 (Syntax Glorious), 2024 (Syntax Expansion) and 2025 (Syntax Learning Organization).

Fig 4: Milestone Syntax Group

In addition to the vision designed for the next 5 years, the Syntax Group leadership has thought of all the ideas and ideas for a very long period of 40 years in the future up to 2065. This is so that the Syntax Group company can last up to several generations in the future, ideas and ideas this is the fruit of the mind of our leader Dr. Taufik Ridwan., M.Hum to be able to compete in the future to the world stage, if you look at the current vision, it is only 5 years and in the future a 40 year Development Master Plan (Milestone) is made divided into 10 year plans including: 1) In 2025 to be

the prima donna of companies in Indonesia 2) In 2035 to be the prima donna of companies in Southeast Asia 3) In 2045 to be the prima donna of companies in Asia 4) In 2055 to be the prima donna of companies in Asia and Europe and 5) In 2065 to be the prima donna of companies throughout the continent . An overview of Syntax Corporation milestones for the next 40 years/65 years is illustrated in the image below.

Fig 5: Milestone Syntax Group for the next 40 years

Syntax Corporation's vision is implemented in an HR empowerment program namely with the name Syntax Man, this syntax man is a fundamental that all Syntax HR must have in carrying out work activities both internally and externally with the aim of providing benefits to many parties. Human Syntax consists of 5 (five) aspects illustrated in the image below.

Figure 6: Human Syntax Group

Human Syntax consists of 5 (five) aspects, namely:

- 1) People of Publication, reflected by having a work of publication proven on Scopus ID, Google Scholar ID and having 10 accredited national and internationally accredited scope articles.
- 2) Human Qualifications, Qualified Humans are reflected by having a high educational qualification of at least Strata 2/S2, so that all HR at Syntax are given scholarships to continue their education.
- 3) Moral Man, this Man reflects high obedience to Allah SWT as evidenced by the culture of Dhuha Prayer and reciting QS. Al-Mulk every day in the morning, and has polite, humble, polite ethics and personality and spreads kindness to anyone.
- 4) Sharing Humans, is reflected in Syntax Group employees so they can have a generous spirit and like to help others. Integrity is built as a carrier of good for anyone. By implementing it at an Educational Institution belonging to the Syntax Group which accommodates several Orphans and Orphans to be able to go to school for free.
- 5) Human Competence, by looking at the pace of the world of business and science that continues to develop, therefore Syntax Group implements and requires all employees to have at least 7 main competencies, so they can become experts in certain fields.

4.6 Syntax Corporation Indonesia as Company Organization

The Syntax Group Company is engaged in educational consulting services, IT, publications and lecturer careers. A company whose main activities include planning, designing, producing as well as presenting every type of superior product. Therefore, it is increasingly assured that projects are under the guidance of people who are experts in their fields, and in accordance with well-managed operational procedures, processes and successful completion can be guaranteed.

Syntax Group divides its organizational structure at the top consisting of the President Commissioner, Junior Commissioner, President Director and 3 Board of Directors (Director of Finance and Marketing, Director of Branch and Foundation, Director of Quality and HR), and consists of teams and across divisions and holdings consisting of from 5 (five) divisions namely Quality Assurance Management, Educational Development Consultant, HR Career, Lecturer Career Consultant and Creative Media and 6 (six) holdings namely Ridwan Institute, Indonesian Publication, Green Publisher, Seo Labs, International Journal Labs and Intention. This detailed description is described in the company profile of Syntax Group Cirebon which plays an important role for the company and is considered the spearhead of the establishment of the company, namely:

- 1) Board of Commissioners: Supervises the management of the Company carried out by the Supervisory Board and Directors and provides advice regarding the policies of the Directors in running the Company.
- 2) Supervisory Board: 1) Supervises the Board of Directors in carrying out the technical activities of the company, as well as supervises and evaluates the performance of the Directors, 2) Assesses and approves the plans of the directors regarding general policies, company targets, allocation of funding sources, and marketing directions, 3) Assists the directors in important tasks.

- 3) The Board of Directors: 1) Implement company policies and take responsibility for work periodically or at the end of work to shareholders, 2) Maintain the stability of the company's organization and maintain good relations between shareholders, leaders and employees, 3) Appoint and dismiss section heads with the approval of the shareholder meeting, 4) Coordinating, organizing, and supervising the implementation of the work of the heads of sections that are his subordinates.
- 4) Finance and Data Manager: 1) Plans and manages the company's operational financial budget 2) Prepares financial reports according to accounting guidelines 3) Ensures financial transactions run in an orderly manner 4) Manages company taxes properly 5) Controls company cash flow 6) Archives company legality documents 7) Compile document documents incoming and outgoing company.
- 5) Holding/Division Director: Coordinate, organize, and supervise the work of talent in the Holding/Division, 2) Responsible to the Board of Directors in the areas of Product, Finance, Marketing and HR.
- 6) Design: The design team by the designers in the Division/Holding, is the spearhead in delivering the company's achievements. The design team is always consistent with creative and highly experienced human beings, which helps in company branding, as well as assists in the marketing process.
- 7) Talent: 1) Carry out operational activities in carrying out the tasks given by the Director according to the directions and KPIs.

5. DISCUSSION

The Syntax Group Cirebon company has an influential culture with a clear vision, mission and regulations. Therefore, the Syntax Group Cirebon Company has written rules and unwritten rules that become the organizational culture. From the written rules, there are rules that become the organizational culture of leaders in improving employee performance, including: briefings, reading the Qur'an every Friday, scientific studies, training and education of cadres. As for the unwritten rules in the Six (6S) (smile, greet, greet, courtesy and enthusiasm). From these rules, organizational culture can improve the performance of Syntax company employees. These rules are written and unwritten rules that become an organizational culture that can improve employee performance.

- a) *briefings*; one of the activities that is always done for 30 minutes before activities in the office. This briefing is carried out every morning with the aim of conducting a simple evaluation of each performance achievement that has been carried out before.
- b) Reading the Qur'an every Friday, is one of the activities that is routinely carried out, namely by reading Al Mulk's letter for employees who are proficient in reading the Qur'an. Meanwhile, for those who are not proficient, assistance is provided to employees.
- c) Scientific studies, is one of the employee upgrading programs that aims to improve the quality of the company's employees. This study apart from updating employee knowledge is also one of the company's strategies in improving the quality of the Company's human resources

- d) Training, is a delegation program if needed. Another program of company upgrading is to equip employees in terms of employee soft skills and hard skills
- e) Cadre education is one of the programs that really supports the HR career path in the company. The company strives to support its employees in continuing their higher education.

Company employees have a desire to grow and make breakthroughs and work more orderly. Not only from one aspect, the Syntax Group has very close family values, so these family values encourage employee enthusiasm in creating a company with a real vision. One of the company's strategies in improving its performance is to support employees to continue their education to a higher level. In addition to building the organizational culture that has been formed, Syntax Group also provide rewards to employees who have higher performance achievements than what has been targeted. Of course this motivates employees to compete in improving their performance. Because basically, when employees get rewards or awards, employees themselves have their own satisfaction and pride for company employees.

Syntax Group activities are based on increasing work competence, productivity, discipline, behavior, and capacity at the level of proficiency and specific skills with the level and qualifications of the position or profession. One way is through the implementation of performance training strategies. This is done so that employees are able to carry out their duties and meet work demands and challenges. Related to this, the Syntax company carries out coaching and guidance for the world of work.

Syntax Group is one of the educational and publication services. Therefore, regarding the development of organizational culture, Syntax Group companies need support from all elements of employees or divisions or institutions in the company. This is done in order to get an accurate picture of performance so that you know more clearly the procedures for employee performance categories, patterns and forms of capacity, which match work needs, technological advances and development.

As previously explained, Syntax Group adheres to important moral and spirit values that motivate the creation of a strong, healthy and competitive work climate. The company's important values that have been carried out consistently and commitment have led the Syntax company to achieve optimal and sustainable performance. This is the basis of organizational culture in improving the performance of Syntax Company employees.

In addition to the learning organization, Syntax Group have an applied work culture. This is as explained in the initial discussion, that the organizational culture of Syntax is 1). Religious, 2). Excellent Service, 3). Innovative, 4). Creative, and 5). Totality. This work culture is the spearhead of the company's development and progress. This is what Syntax Company has done service performance with the Fast, Complete, and Satisfied model, as previously described (CTP). This model is one of the company's uniqueness in providing user satisfaction.

Employees are given direction from the various cultures of the organization. Briefing is carried out as an effort to improve the employee's spirituality. With spiritual improvement, employees will implement positive values within the Company. Syntax Group also organizes activities aimed at strengthening family values. Strong kinship makes employees work well together. Third, through regulations. Regulations are made so that employees do not act arbitrarily. With the prohibitions and regulations of

the company, employees need to comply with these regulations. Employees who violate the prohibitions and regulations will get the consequences that have been made. With these cultures, employees need to accept and familiarize themselves with the rules that exist within the company.

In achieving goals, the Syntax Group has arranged a form of institution and a real culture, so that employees do not encounter any significant difficulties or obstacles while on duty. On the other hand, the Syntax company has a good organizational structure so that it can achieve the goals and achieve the company's vision effectively and efficiently. It can also be useful in an effort to increase optimal results and to protect the viability and future of Syntax Group.

Some of the factors forming attitudes towards employee performance at the Syntax Company are as follows:

- 1) Skills/knowledge acquired can affect performance results
- 2) Company leaders have an important role in improving the quality of employee performance
- 3) High absentee levels can affect the increase in employee performance

Syntax Group has a dominant Culture with clear vision, mission and rules. From here it can be observed that cultural characteristics are orientation towards results and innovation towards taking risks. Employees find hope for development and innovation and work more disciplined. Apart from getting compensation, employees also have very strong family values, so this family value drives employee motivation in building the company for a clear vision.

Syntax Group management is very optimal in carrying out its responsibilities, the company carries out employee selection and conducts formal training so that employee expertise can reach the given stage. So that employees get motivation to compete with other employees. The sense of kinship also creates several factors for the high level of competence of employees at Syntax companies. This is based on elements of the dominant culture within the Syntax company.

Syntax company also has another culture which is service culture. That element is good communication and prioritizing product quality, good communication helps employees in forming good team coordination. Good coordination on work affects efficiency within the company. Strong family values have a positive impact on team coordination and communication. Collaboration between employees and divisions and holdings owned by Syntax companies implements an excellent organizational culture.

From the explanation above, the following is the researcher conveying the results of the interviews in this study.

Table 1: Interview Results

No.	Question	Answer	Respondents
1.	What is the company's strategy in improving employee performance?	So the strategy is to equalize thoughts, then after we have the same thoughts then we act on it in a system and we create a culture that is clear, for example, is a culture about <i>briefings</i> , reading the Koran every Friday, scientific studies, training and education of cadres.	Director of Quality and Marketing
2.	How do employees understand the vision	We are given time to socialize the work environment. So every employee, especially new ones, is involved	President Director

	and mission of the company?	in socialization activities regarding the vision and mission as well as the job description.	
3.	Does the company have organizational cultural values.?	So this company has cultural values that guide employees, that is as explained in the existing company profile, even the ultimate goal of having these cultural values is to become a human being with syntax, as in the company profile. When it comes to the organizational culture of this company, it just so happens that it has its own basis, namely work culture and work values which are summarized in the slogan fast, complete, and satisfied.	Director of Quality and Marketing
4.	Does the culture exist that all employees participate in these activities?	So activities that have been scheduled by the company or program person in charge. We like to follow scientific studies conducted by the president director. For example about leadership or leadership. Maybe this is important for employees, because it can increase employee independence at work. Or sometimes the program is related to technology.	Director of Quality and Marketing
5.	Do you think work culture can improve employee performance?	The work culture is driven from within myself, as for that I am fertilizer from the science earlier, the motivations earlier so from that culture I gave the scientific knowledge and the motivations earlier	President Director
6.	Does the company always provide direction in work?	We have briefings every day before work. So this briefing becomes part of the organizational culture as well, because for us . So each of our programs is directed and clear, according to the company's targets and achievements. Or the briefing is also a space for conveying new ideas or any information related to our work. So this briefing only takes 15-30 minutes, every day there so that the work is focused	President Director
7.	How do companies build teams within the company?	Indeed, at Syntax, the value of togetherness and kinship is very high, bro. So yes, I also felt it, at first I asked that sometimes I don't even know that we were formed because of a situation to help each other when working as a team, for example in one holding we strengthen and help each other. In fact, we at the company have activities that specifically aim to build togetherness, for example family gatering, or Parent Day activities which are specifically dedicated to the parents of employees. So what you don't realize, indirectly we really care about this company, bro.	President Director
8.	What is the company doing to improve employee performance	The first is always evaluating the work of each unit head or head of the institution, we hold a dialogue, then we hold what is called, the achievement strategy of each unit, so they must know the target, what the strategy is, how to achieve it, and then there is communication, so there is intense communication between unit heads of institutions and below	Director of Quality and Marketing
9.	Do you know about the organizational cultural values of the Syntax Group company?	So, as stated in our company profile, bro, we have a tagline or a guide for us to motivate our performance. The taglen is in the form of work culture values and our company's cultural values which are displayed in every strategic place for employees to see. There is even a corporate ethical culture, namely 6S (smile, greet, greet, polite, courteous, grateful)	Head of Division/ Holding
10.	Does the company have regulations to control the performance of its employees?	The rules, yes, those for controlling performance, of course, the rules for filling out the checklist must be in place, so the salary isn't there. If the checklist isn't there, that's why they make the checklist, there are lots of work regulations, for example, regulations related to discipline, regulations related to anything.	Director of Quality and Marketing

		the name earlier was eee reward, punnishmen, that's it	
11.	How does the company build a sense of kinship among employees	I instill a sense of belonging with a sense of kinship so they feel so if the kinship is strong, we feel that this is my family, so it feels as if this really belongs to me, so the feeling of love for conscience is strong, from that feeling of love comes a defense for conscience and all upgrades	President Director
12.	How does the company improve employee commitment	If it's my commitment, yes, this is ours, we built this social foundation for the community for orphans, underprivileged children, so working here is for worship, that's all	Director of Quality and Marketing
13.	How does the company improve employee competence	So here, if there are employees who want to continue their studies or college, the company really supports them. Of course the company's way of providing many opportunities and at the same time assistance from the company when its employees are studying while working. That's why employees are also more enthusiastic because besides being able to work while also being supported, employees are supported to improve the quality of their human resources	Director of Quality and Marketing
14.	What kind of monitoring system is carried out by the company in improving performance?	So in the Syntax Group company, it has been divided according to the holding and divisions under the auspices of the company. Each division and holding head is directly responsible to superiors. Then see whether the program achievements in each program have been running, and also whether the division targets have been achieved or not. And this is done every month	President Director
15.	What is the benchmark for performance improvement?	As stated earlier, the performance measurement in this company is the achievement of each division, the targets that have been agreed upon by the division heads and superiors are then evaluated every month, if there is a decline in the performance of each division then find out the problems and constraints. Only then, if you already know the problems and constraints, the company will hold routine training or studies that have been programmed by the company	Director of Quality and Marketing
16.	At what time is the employee performance evaluation process?	So each division head or holding company makes a monthly evaluation, that's where the evaluation process is.	Head of Division/ Holding

Source: Author processed, 2023

The Syntax Corporation is thick in the interest of service quality, here it is observed in the organizational culture characteristics of the concern for Fast Results, Completely Satisfied (CTP) as the work values built by the Syntax company. Syntax company employees work with regularity and have sharp accuracy to maintain service quality. From here can be generated satisfaction and loyalty of company users. Syntax Group have work values and work culture that become a reference in achieving the goals or vision of the organization. Of course this is supported by the premise of building this company with the spirit of learning together or in terms this company calls it a learning organization, and this is an achievement of the company. learning organization means that the company continues to carry out a learning culture so that it continues to grow and develop.

One of the intended learning organization achievements is dynamic learning. That the entire team is required to carry out continuous learning dynamics in order to create learning humans, transforming organizations. From here, it is hoped that the company will continue to transform according to the needs and challenges of the times. People empowerment is also intended to continue to empower both internally and externally. Knowledge management is intended to apply existing management within the organization and technology application is intended for companies to apply technology applications in the company's development process. The President Commissioner of the Syntax Group Company stated that there are various kinds of characteristics and characteristics that exist in the organization, including:

- 1) Individual initiative is an employee's thought to find answers to every problem. Initiative is also an employee's sensitivity to work that is not even their responsibility. At Syntax Company, every employee is allowed to take the initiative freely but in accordance with his Job Discretion. Syntax company gives space to its employees to take initiative. They can develop ideas that they feel capable of developing the Syntax Company. Thus, work is quickly completed without orders from superiors.
- 2) Tolerance for risky actions is a good decision when implemented in a company. At Syntax Company, employees are allowed to act more actively and aggressively. This is allowed with the aim of building and advancing the Syntax Company. Syntax Company Leaders intend that employees are more daring to act and dare to take risks for their actions.

Syntax Company employees are given space to act aggressively and innovatively. An employee is allowed to discover new things and find new ideas in completing his work. It is intended that employees are able to take action and be responsible for all the risks taken. With aggressive and innovative actions, employees are considered to have a sense of love for Syntax Company so that they act more actively in order to advance Syntax Company.

- 3) Direction is an action ordered by the organization in achieving goals. The briefing aims so that organizations can clearly create the desired goals and expectations. As is the case at Syntax Company, this company has hopes that employees can be more useful for the wider community.

Briefings at Syntax Company are carried out every day during briefings. With direction, employees will know what is right and what is wrong. The purpose of directing employees is to keep employees focused and not deviate from the main goal. Therefore, the leadership of Syntax Company always gives direction to its employees every day.

- 4) Integration is the leader's action in encouraging each unit head in managing the company's units. Apart from encouraging them to work better, a leader needs to make the right strategy. The right strategy makes each business unit well-coordinated. The Syntax company has several Division and Holding units, including: Division; Quality Assurance Management, Educational Development Consultant, HR Career, Creative Media, SCI Media, Participatory Economic Agency. Dan Holding; Syntax Publishing, Intention, Ridwan Institute, Indonesian Publication, Green Publishing, Seolabs.

- 5) Management support is an effort made by leaders to motivate their employees. Leaders need to provide clear direction, assistance, and support to subordinates. As in the Syntax Company, leaders always provide materials such as leadership at the time that has been provided. It aims to make employees more aware of their responsibilities and enthusiasm for work.
- 6) Motivation makes employees more enthusiastic at work. Employees will recall what factors pushed them to work. At Syntax Company there are two motivations. The motivation is external motivation and internal motivation. External motivation is motivation that arises from within individuals who are influenced by other factors. While internal motivation is motivation that arises from within the person.
- 7) Control is monitoring the limits that may be done by an employee. These boundaries are usually in the form of regulations or norms that apply within an organization. With rules, employees will learn to obey and prevent what may not be done in the company. The control system at Syntax Company uses company regulations.
- 8) Controlling employees is an important job that a leader does for his employees. Syntax Company Leaders control the work of their employees through two types, namely through observation and work results. The leader observes through observation by looking directly at the employees at work. These observations are seen in terms of attitude, behavior, and so forth.
- 9) The reward system is an expression of gratitude given in the form of money, facilities, and so on. The reward system is given based on employee performance. The reward system is given not because of seniority and favoritism. In Syntax Company, the reward system is calculated based on the performance of each employee. The reward system at Syntax Company looks at how the employee is performing at that time. If employees work well, then employees get a lot of income. Conversely, if employees work poorly, the income they get will decrease.
- 10) Tolerance for conflict is the extent to which employees are encouraged to express conflict and criticism. At Syntax Company, every employee is allowed to raise a conflict. For the most part, employees handle conflicts between employees in a personal way. If the conflict is not resolved, the leadership will handle it. Every company faces various kinds of conflicts. Conflicts that occur are not only about work conflicts but also conflicts between employees. Syntax Company allows employees to express work conflicts and conflicts between employees. Conflicts between employees are resolved individually or mutually forgiven
- 11) The pattern of communication is very important in fostering relationships between employees. Companies have two patterns of communication, namely formal communication and informal communication. Formal communication is communication that is used for evaluation and resolution of problems or matters of a serious nature. Informal communication is communication that is used for situations between employees, friendships and approaches within the company. At Syntax Company, communication is created so that employees are more familiar and know each other. Leaders often make several events or activities so that their employees communicate well.

- 12) The communication pattern contained in the Syntax Company is considered very good. Every employee communicates well every time they work. The leader's strategy in establishing communication between employees is by means of joint sports, gatherings, programs for employees' families, eating together and so on.

6. CONCLUSION

As in the theoretical studies that have been explained in the previous discussion, in human resource management, in Syntax Group companies, in improving employee performance, planning has been carried out to build commitment regarding strategies for achieving the company's vision to build an organizational culture in order to create company quality. The Syntax Company has a dominant culture with a clear vision, mission, and rules. This can be seen from the core culture or the Work Culture of the Syntax Group Company, which includes Religious, Excellent Service, Innovative, Creative, and Totality. Then, in implementing employee performance improvement strategies, Syntax Company supports the creation of optimal employee performance by building cultural values or with Syntax Group Work Values; these include satisfaction, completion, and speed. Therefore, Syntax Company has achieved its achievements by developing strategies to achieve company goals with dynamic learning, organization transformation, people empowerment, knowledge management, and technology applications. As explained in theory, empowering human resources improves performance by encouraging competence and creating an organizational climate to produce competent employees. From these achievements, the Syntax Group Company is committed to building Syntax Human Resources (Syntax people). From the formation of Syntax, humans will give birth to competent employees, self-concept, character, knowledge, skills, and work motivation. The formation of Syntax people and this cultural climate are the keys to achieving optimal company performance so that the company's quality continues to increase.

References

- 1) Abdi, Nurgunawan, & Wahid, Muhsin. (2018). The influence of competence and work environment on employee performance. *PARADOX: Journal of Economics*, 1(1), 66–81.
- 2) Aisyah, Merisa Fajar, Utami, Wiji, Sunardi, Sunardi, & Sudarsih, Sudarsih. (2017). Quality of Human Resources, Work Professionalism, and Commitment as Supporting Factors for Improving Employee Performance at PDAM Jember Regency. *E-Journal of Business Economics and Accounting*, 4(1), 131. <https://doi.org/10.19184/ejeba.v4i1.4753>
- 3) Akbar, Surya. (2018). Analysis of factors that affect employee performance. *Jiaganis*, 3(1).
- 4) Akin, S. (2010). Impact of work teams performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 225.
- 5) Aliastuti, Sri. (2017). The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance at PT. BPR Fiankan Rezalina Fatma Pekanbaru. Riau Islamic University.
- 6) Ásványi, Zsófia. (2022). *Strategic Human Resource Management*.
- 7) Ayunda, Cherly, Siswati, Endang, & Faith, Nurul. (2021). The Influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Emotional Intelligence and Work Environment on Employee Performance at PT. Heritage in Sidoarjo. *UBHARA Management Journal*, 1(1), 145–151.
- 8) Get up, Wilson. (2008). Organizational Culture: Its impact on increasing company competitiveness. *Maranatha Journal of Management*, 8(1), 38–49.
- 9) Bergman, Jacqueline Z., Rentsch, Joan R., Small, Erika E., Davenport, Shaun W., & Bergman, Shawn M. (2012). The shared leadership process in decision-making teams. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 152(1), 17–42.

- 10) Bintoro, Daryanto, & Daryanto, Drs. (2017). Employee performance appraisal management. Yogyakarta: Gava Media, 15.
- 11) Bowen, David E., & Lawler, EE (1994). The empowerment of service workers: What, why, how and when. The Training and Development Sourcebook, HRD Press Inc., Amherst, 413–422.
- 12) Burke, WW (2005). Leadership as empowering others, In S. Srivatra (Ed), Executive Power. Sanfrancisco, Jossey-Boss.
- 13) Callista, Natasha. (2016). The Effect of HR Competence on Employee Performance at PT. Tresnamuda Sejati Surabaya Branch. *Agora*, 4(2), 45–50.
- 14) Cartwright, Nancy, & McMullin, Ernan. (1984). How the laws of physics lie. American Association of Physics Teachers.
- 15) Creswell, John W., & Poth, CN (2007). Choosing among five approaches. *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- 16) Dessler, Gary. (2015). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 17) Fatchurrohman, Rudy. (2011). The effect of achievement motivation on learning readiness, apprenticeship implementation and achievement of productive subject competencies. *Invotec*, 7(2).
- 18) Friedman, W., & Casner-Lotto, J. (2002). The power of teamwork. *Worklife Report*, 14(1), 8–9.
- 19) Ghosh, Ajit Kumar. (2013). Employee empowerment: A strategic tool to obtain sustainable competitive advantage. *International Journal of Management*, 30(3), 95.
- 20) Glassop, Linda I. (2002). The organizational benefits of teams. *Human Relations*, 55(2), 225–249.
- 21) Greasley, Kay, Bryman, Alan, Dainty, Andrew, Price, Andrew, Naismith, Nicola, & Soetanto, Robby. (2008). Understanding empowerment from an employee perspective: What does it mean and do they want it? *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*.
- 22) Gumilang, Galang Surya. (2016). Qualitative Research Methods in Guidance and Counseling. *Journal of Counseling Focus*, 2(2). Retrieved from <http://ejournal.stkipmpringsewu-lpg.ac.id/index.php/Fokus/a>
- 23) Herdiansyah, Singgih, & Prastiwi, Andri. (2012). The influence of information characteristics of management accounting systems and decentralization on managerial performance with environmental uncertainty as a moderating variable. Faculty of Economics and Business.
- 24) <http://www.dikti.go.id/industri-jasa-had-potential-against-peningkatan-economy-indonesia>
- 25) <http://www.beritasatu.com/economy/353695- already-time-indonesia-focus-di-sector-jasa.html>
- 26) Irfan, Fahmi. (2012). *Management (Theory, Cases, and Solutions)*. Second Print, Alfabeta Cv, Bandung.
- 27) Ismail, Solihin. (2012). *Strategic Management*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- 28) Jaja, Jahari, & Sutikno, M. Sobry. (2008). *Human Resource Management*. Bandung: Prospects.
- 29) Kadir, S. and Nasrul. (2018). "The Influence of Competence and Work Discipline on Employee Performance (The Effect Of Competence And Discipline Of Work On Performance Of Employees)." *Journal of Management, Business, and Organizations*, 2(2), 22–28.
- 30) Kartika, Lucia Nurbani, & Sugiarto, Agus. (2016). The Effect of Competency Level on the Performance of Office Administration Employees. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 17(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.24914/jeb.v17i1.240>
- 31) Kirkman, Bradley L., & Rosen, Benson. (1997). A model of work team empowerment. *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, 10(1), 131–167.
- 32) Kirkman, Bradley L., & Rosen, Benson. (2000). Powering up teams. *Organizational Dynamics*.
- 33) Kirkman, Bradley L., Rosen, Benson, Tesluk, Paul E., & Gibson, Cristina B. (2004). The impact of team empowerment on virtual team performance: The moderating role of face-to-face interaction. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(2), 175–192.

- 34) Korsgaard, M. Audrey, Soyoung Jeong, Sophia, Mahony, Douglas M., & Pitariu, Adrian H. (2008). A multilevel view of intragroup conflict. *Journal of Management*, 34(6), 1222–1252.
- 35) Kotlyar, Igor, & Karakowsky, Leonard. (2006). Leading conflicts? Linkages between leader behaviors and group conflict. *Small Group Research*, 37(4), 377–403.
- 36) Kuokkanen, Liisa, Leino-Kilpi, Helena, & Katajisto, Jouko. (2003). Nurse empowerment, job-related satisfaction, and organizational commitment. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 18(3), 184–192.
- 37) Langfred, Claus W. (2000). The paradox of self-management: Individual and group autonomy in work groups. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 21(5), 563–585.
- 38) Langfred, Claus W. (2007). The downside of self-management: A longitudinal study of the effects of conflict on trust, autonomy, and task interdependence in self-managing teams. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(4), 885–900.
- 39) Laschinger, Heather K. Spence, Finegan, Joan, Shamian, Judith, & Wilk, Piotr. (2001). Impact of structural and psychological empowerment on job strains in nursing work settings: expanding Kanter's model. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 31(5), 260–272.
- 40) Leady, P., & Ormrod, J.E. (2005). *Practical research. Planning and Design*.
- 41) Liestiati, Tuty Sri. (2020). Analysis Of The Influence Of Professional Competence, Credibility, And Emotional Intelligence On Pilot Performance. *Scientific Journal Of Reflection: Economics, Accounting, Management and Business*, 3(3), 311–320.
- 42) Lupiyoadi, Rambat, & Hamdani, A. (2013). *Service marketing management*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- 43) Mahendrawan, I. Gede, & Indrawati, Ayu Desi. (2015). *Effect of workload and compensation on job satisfaction PT. Panca Dewata Denpasar*. Udayana University.
- 44) Manialup, Angel Wulandari, Nangoi, Grace B., & Morasa, Jenny. (2017). The Role of the Inspectorate in the Implementation of the Government's Internal Control System in the Regional Government of the Talaud Islands Regency. *Journal Of Accounting And Auditing Research" Goodwill"*, 8(2).
- 45) Miles, Matthew B., & Huberman, A. Michael. (1992). *Qualitative data analysis*. Jakarta: UI Press.
- 46) Mitchell, Terence R., Holtom, Brooks C., Lee, Thomas W., Sablynski, Chris J., & Erez, Miriam. (2001). Why people stay: Using job affiliation to predict voluntary turnover. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(6), 1102–1121.
- 47) Moleong, Lexy J. (2000). *Qualitative research methodology*, cet. XI. Bandung: PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
- 48) Moleong, Lexy J. (2007). *Qualitative research methods*. Bandung: rosdakarya youth.
- 49) Moleong, Lexy J. (2021). *Qualitative research methodology*. PT Juvenile Rosdakarya.
- 50) Mowen, Maryanne M., Hansen, Don R., & Heitger, Dan L. (2016). *Managerial accounting: The cornerstone of business decision-making*. Cengage Learning.
- 51) Mulyadi, Deddy. (2015). *Organizational behavior and service leadership*. Bandung: Alfabet.
- 52) Mulyadi, Hari. (2010). The Effect of Work Motivation and Competence on Employee Work Productivity at PT. Galamedia Bandung Mighty. *Managerial: Journal of Management and Information Systems*, 9(2), 97–111.
- 53) Myers, Michael D., & Newman, Michael. (2007). The qualitative interview in IS research: Examining the craft. *Information and Organization*, 17(1), 2–26.
- 54) Nasution, S. (2003). *Qualitative Naturalistic Research Methods (Bandung)*. Tarsito. Libraries. Fis. Uny. Air conditioning. Id/Opac/Index. Php.
- 55) Nilamsari, Natalina. (2014). Understanding Document Studies in Qualitative Research. *Discourse*, 13(2), 177–181.

- 56) Nurmianto, Eko, & Siswanto, Nurhadi. (2006). Design of Employee Performance Assessment Based on Spencer's Competency Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process Method (Case Study in the Irrigation Sub-Department of the Public Works Office, Probolinggo City). *Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 8(1), 40–53.
- 57) Pabundu, Tika. (2008). *Organizational Culture and Company Performance Improvement: Earth Literacy*. Jakarta.
- 58) Panggabean, Mutiara Sibarani. (2009). Basic Nature of Human Resource Management. 1–68.
- 59) Pfeffer, J., Soetjipto, BW, & Handoko, TH (2003). *New Paradigm of Human Resource Management*, Editor A. Usmara, Fourth Printing, Second Edition. Yogyakarta: Amara Books Publisher.
- 60) Prati, L. Melita, Douglas, Ceasar, Ferris, Gerald R., Ammeter, Anthony P., & Buckley, M. Ronald. (2003). Emotional intelligence, leadership effectiveness, and team outcomes. *The International Journal of Organizational Analysis*.
- 61) Psinos, Anna, & Smithson, Steve. (2002). Employee empowerment in manufacturing: a study of organizations in the UK. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 17(2), 132–148.
- 62) Rahardjo, Mudjia. (2017). *Case Studies in Qualitative Research*. ĐĐµÑ Ñ ,Đ½ĐĐo Đ Đ¾Ñ Đ· ĐÑ€ ĐĐ2Đ½ĐĐĐ· Đ¾Ñ€ Đ.
- 63) Rahmawanti, Nela Pima. (2014). The influence of the work environment on employee performance (Study on employees of the North Malang Primary tax service office). Brawijaya University.
- 64) Randolph, W. Alan, & Sashkin, Marshall. (2002). Can organizational empowerment work in multinational settings? *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 16(1), 102–115.
- 65) Raub, Steffen, & Robert, Christopher. (2010). Differential effects of empowering leadership on in-role and extra-role employee behaviors: Exploring the role of psychological empowerment and power values. *Human Relations*, 63(11), 1743–1770.
- 66) Ritchhart, Ron, Church, Mark, & Morrison, Karin. (2014). *Hacer visible el pensamiento*. Grupo Planeta Spain.
- 67) Rizal, Yosep, & Hubeis, Musa et al. (2013). The influence of competency factors on individual performance in agro-industry companies going public. *SME Management: Journal of Small and Medium Industry Development Management*, 8(1), 1–8.
- 68) Rizky, Pratama, Wahjusaputri, Sintha, & Wibowo, Adityo Ari. (2020). The Influence of Work Discipline and Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction of Pizza Hut Employees in the East Jakarta Region. *Journal of Management Research*, College of Economics, Widya Wiwaha Master of Management Program, 7(2), 105–112.
- 69) Santoso, Eko Boedhi, Fiernaningsih, Nilawati, & Murtiyanto, Rizky Kurniawan. (2018). The Influence of Organizational Culture on Organizational Performance. *Adbis: Journal of Administration and Business*, 12(1), 40–45.
- 70) Sarosa, Samiji. (2012). *Qualitative research: The basics*.
- 71) Sedarmayanti, S. (2017). *HR Planning and Development to Improve Competency, Performance, and Work Productivity*. Bandung: Publisher PT. Aditama Refika.
- 72) Sekaran, Uma, & Bougie, Roger. (2016). *Research Methods For Business: A Skill Building Approach* (7th ed.). United Kingdom: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- 73) Soegijono, MS (1993). Interview as one method of data collection. *Health Research and Development Media*, 3(1), 157152.
- 74) Somantri, Gumilar Rusliwa. (2010). Understand qualitative methods. *Hubs-Asia*, 10(1).
- 75) Spreitzer, Gretchen M. (2008). Taking stock: A review of more than twenty years of research on empowerment at work. *Handbook of Organizational Behavior*, 1, 54–72.
- 76) Spreitzer, Gretchen M., Kizilos, Mark A., & Nason, Stephen W. (1997). A dimensional analysis of the relationship between psychological empowerment and effectiveness satisfaction, and strain. *Journal of Management*, 23(5), 679–704.

- 77) Suputra, IDNSA, & Sriathi, AA Ayu. (2018). Effect of work motivation and job satisfaction on organizational commitment. *Unud Management E-Journal*, 7(9), 4628–4656.
- 78) Walton, E. Richard. (1985). From control to commitment in the Workplace, *Harvard Business Review*, March-April.
- 79) Waspodo, Agung AWS, Handayani, Nurul Chotimah, & et al. (2013). The effect of job satisfaction and work stress on turnover intention at PT. Unitex in bogor. *JRMSI-Indonesian Science Management Research Journal*, 4(1), 97–115.
- 80) Wibowo, Endro, & Utomo, Hardi. (2016). The effect of occupational safety and occupational health on performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable (a case study of employees in the effervescent powder production unit at PT Sido Muncul Semarang). *Among Makarti*, 9(1).
- 81) Widjoyo, Iksan Ongko. (2013). Analysis of the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction at McDonald's Basuki Rahmat drive thru services in Surabaya. *Marketing Strategy Journal*, 1(1).
- 82) Widodo, Hyginus Suseno Triyanto, & Triwanggono, Aloysius. (2018). Characteristics of Organizational Culture, Adaptability, and Performance of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. *EXERO: Journal of Research in Business and Economics*, 1(1), 90–110.
- 83) Wijoyo, Hadion, & Juita, Audia. (2021). *Superior HR in Industry 4.0 - Hadion Wijoyo* - Google Books.
- 84) Wolcott, Harry F. (1994). *Transforming qualitative data: Description, analysis, and interpretation*. Sage.